

Evaluation of Functional and Chemical Properties of Composite Flour made from Unripe Plantain (*Musa Paradisiaca*) and Cocoyam (*Colocasia Esculenta*) and Assessment of Consumers' Acceptability of Amala

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Abstract: The study evaluated the functional and chemical properties of composite flour produced using unripe plantain and cocoyam and consumer acceptability of amala. Unripe plantain and cocoyam tests acquired from Orie-ugba market in Umuahia were washed, stripped, cut and dried in a stove for 24 h at 60 °C albeit the cocoyam cuts were drenched for 6 h with irregular difference in water after each 2 h. The doused cocoyam was rewashed, depleted and whitened for 4 minutes followed by drying in a broiler at 57±3 °C and processing to get flour test. The two flours (plantain flour: cocoyam flour), were formed into various extents, 40:60: 50:50 and 60:40. The control was 100 % plantain. The examples were exposed to examinations utilizing standard techniques. The aftereffects of the functional properties showed that the mass thickness went from 0.77 to 0.91 g/ml, gelatinization limit 8-12 enlarging record 29.12 to 34.02 while water ingestion limit went from 1.29 to 3.64 g/ml. The pH values went from 5.88 to 6.75. Test B(100% cocoyam flour) had the most noteworthy flavonoid content of 49.75 mg while test A (100 percent plantain flour) had the least worth (0.67 mg). The carotenoid content went from 0.73 to 48.82 µg. Test B was fundamentally unique (p<0.05) from different examples regarding all phenolics. Test A was most liked.

Keywords: Amala, Chemical composition, Cocoyam, Composite flour, Consumers' acceptability, Functional properties, Unripe plantain

1. Introduction

Amala is a conventional term used to depict thick glues ready by mixing flour from cocoyam, unripe plantain or cassava, from sweet potato, cocoyam, cassava or unripe plantain in a bubbling water to frame smooth consistency (Fetuga et al., 2014). It is a famous bland ethnic "Fufu" like feast ordinarily eaten by ethnic Yorubas of South-Western Nigeria. It is progressively consumed among non-ethnic Yoruba consumer in Nigeria and a few different nations in the Western shoreline of Nigeria (Idowu et al., 2017).

Plantain (*Musa paradisiaca L.*) is a significant staple harvest, providing up to 25% of the sugars for roughly 70 million individuals in sticky zone of sub-Saharan Africa. The plant comprises long, covering leafstalks with a stem which is 1.22 to 6.10 meter high while the leaves develop to a length of 1.83 meter and 0.61 meter wide. The unripe plantain is utilized in legends medication for treating loose bowels, diarrhea, and gastrointestinal sores in ulcerative colitis, diabetes, uremia, nephritis, gout, hypertension and cardiovascular illness (Ghani, 2003). In Nigeria, it is extremely normal to find diabetic patients consuming unripe plantain feast to lessen postprandial glucose level. This is on the grounds that the inclination of people to foster diabetes and weight is because of the expanded utilization of sugar rich food varieties with a high glycemic profile (Willet et al., 2002). Plantains are great wellsprings of plant phytochemicals (Ghani, 2003) which advances wellbeing and prosperity.

As per FAO (2009), over 2.3 million metric lots of plantains are created in Nigeria every year; it is a boring, less sweet assortment of banana that can be utilized in unripe form or ready. They are priceless wellspring of starch, practically identical in nutritive worth to sweet potato, cocoyam or potato and are valuable as a variation on the typical staple food varieties. In Nigeria, plantain is mostly eaten as bites in the form of ikire, chips, and dodo. Plantain can be consumed as ready or unripe in a few structures: it can be boiled, simmered, steamed, heated or barbecued. Different items got from plantain could be in type of chips and flour (Nwokocha & Williams, 2009).

In Africa, Asia and the Pacific, Cocoyam (*Colocasia esculenta*) is another type of staple root crop (Temesgen & Retta, 2015). Cocoyam has a place with the Araceae family, *Colocasia esculenta*, also called taro is more famous in Nigeria than *Xanthosoma sagittifolium*, otherwise called tannia (Ijioma et al., 2014). In Nigeria, Cocoyam positions third in significance among all the root crops especially cassava and sweet potato with respect to development and utilization (Olayiwola et al., 2012). It is consumed in Nigerian homes either as bubbled or cooked glue (amala), generally during periods continuing sweet potato reap, and this highlights its significance as a potential substitute for sweet potato (Ajijola et al., 2003). Cocoyam contains around 2.0grams of protein, 31grams of sugar, 1.0grams of fiber, 20 milligram of calcium among other nutritive and nutrients. Cocoyam is utilized as a wellspring of nourishment for man and livestock. Cocoyam can be handled and consumed as fufu, soup thickener, broiled achicha, it tends to be cut into chips and afterward dried; the dried chips can be rehydrated and made into porridge with vegetables, palm oil and oil bean. The study examined the functional and chemical properties of composite flour produced using unripe plantain and cocoyam and consumer acceptability of amala.

1.1. Statement of Problem

Consumers consciousness of the need to eat top notch and quality food known as functional food varieties, that is to say, food sources which contain fixings that give extra medical

advantages past the fundamental dietary prerequisite is expanding (Ndife & Abbo, 2009). Cocoyam is profoundly restorative for diabetic patient on the grounds that its starch content is exceptionally low. It is plentiful in vitamin B6 and this makes it really great for controlling hypertension and safeguards the heart. Plantain is consumed essentially in Nigeria as bites in type of chips, dodo and ikire. All the more thus, plantain and cocoyam contains a low glycemic profile esteem, so they are all the more leisurely processed, retained, used and cause a lower and more slow ascent in blood glucose and are consumed by diabetic patients. Data is anyway sparse on the exhibition of cocoyam-plantain flour mixes in amala. Amala is generally consumed in the Western piece of Nigeria. Notwithstanding, the item is only acquired from sweet potato or cassava flours. Subsequently, there is need to investigate different sources, for example, cocoyam and plantain to improve its dietary benefit and broaden its use processes.

1.2. Justification of the Study

Plantain is a famous dietary staple because of its flexibility and great healthy benefit. It is plentiful in minerals including potassium. Plantain is a decent wellspring of phytochemical similarly cocoyam. Amala has been acquired from cassava and sweet potato. A few scientists have created amala from cassava root and its strip as well as sweet potato tubers and their strip yet none delivered in similar extents with plantain in blend with cocoyam. This study will close this gap in the information.

1.3. Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to evaluate the functional and chemical properties of a composite flour (*Amala*) produced from unripe plantain (*Musa paradisiaca*) and cocoyam (*Colocasia esculenta*) and consumers' acceptability of *amala* made from it.

The specific Purpose of this work were;

- (a) To produce cocoyam and plantain flour blends.
- (b) To determine the functional properties of the flour blends of cocoyam and plantain.
- (c) To evaluate the antioxidants properties of flour blends from cocoyam and plantain.
- (d) To produce *amala* from flour blends of plantain and cocoyam.
- (e) To evaluate the consumer's acceptability of *amala* samples.

2. Materials and Methods

2.1. Design for the Study

The experimental design used for this study was complete randomized design.

2.1.1. Ethics Statement

The study was carried out with informed consent, anonymity, and confidentiality of the respondents who voluntarily participated in the organoleptic study. There was strict compliance with the ethical demands of sensory evaluation as required in research studies.

2.2. Procurement of Raw Materials

Newly harvested cocoyam (*Colocasia esculenta*) and unripe plantain (*Musa paradisiaca L.*) were purchased from Ori-Ugba market, Umuahia, Abia State, Nigeria. Other materials used for processing and in carrying out analysis were accessed at the Biochemistry Laboratory of the National Root Crop Research Institute of Umudike, Abia State.

2.3. Processing of Sample

2.3.1. Production of Cocoyam into Flour

The technique of James et al. (2019) was utilized for the processing of cocoyam into flour. Corms and cormels were figured out, washed completely with clean water, peeled and cut to around 1 cm thickness utilizing a manual kitchen slicer. The cuts were moved into an impeccable pot, covered with water and splashed for 6 hours with discontinuous difference in water after like clockwork. Following 6 hours, the doused cocoyam was rewashed, depleted and whitened for 4 minutes. The cuts were dried in a broiler at 57 ± 3 °C and processed into flour utilizing a miller. The processed sample was sieved with 250 µm screen sifter and put away in hermetically sealed container preceding examination.

2.3.2. Processing of Unripe Plantain Flour

The unripe plantain was handled as portrayed by Azeez et al.(2021). The unripe plantain was washed severally with clean water, stripped, cut to around 5 mm meager, dried in a stove at 60 °C for 24 hours. From there on, the chips were processed into fine flour and kept in a hermetically sealed container until required for examination.

2.3.3. Formulation of the Flour Blends

Table 1: Formulation of composite flour for production of *Amala* samples

Sample Code	Plantain	Cocoyam
A	100	0
B	0	100
C	60	40
D	50	50
E	40	60

2.3.4. Production of *Amala*

Amala was delivered in light of the strategy portrayed by Abbas et al. (2017). The flour mixes was appropriately blended in view of the different plan in a bubbling water and afterward mixed consistently to keep irregularities from framing. Ten (10) minutes was used to prepare the glue at low power after which aluminum foil was used to wrap it and kept at 63 °C for very nearly 3 minutes in an adjusted broiler (to hot-hold *amala*) prior to serving.

2.4. Sample Analysis Technique

2.4.1. Functional Properties

The following functional properties: mass thickness, gelatinization limit, expanding power and water absorption capacity were determined according to the methods portrayed by Onwuka (2018).

2.4.2. Antioxidant Properties of the Flour Samples

The antioxidant properties of the flour samples such as phenolic, flavonoid and carotenoid were determined accordingly Onwuka (2018).

2.4.3. Sensory Evaluation

The sensory boundaries, for example, appearance, mouldability, fragrance, mouth-feel and general acceptability were assessed involving the 9 point hedonic scale as depicted by Iwe (2010).

2.5. Statistical Analysis Technique

Data generated were subjected to a statistical tool (ANOVA) of a completely randomized design (CRD) and expressed as mean value standard deviations. Duncan multiple range test was

used to analyze massive contrast significant difference among the experimental mean values ($p < 0.05$).

3. Results and Discussion

3.1. Evaluation of the Functional Properties of the Flour Samples

The outcome introduced in table 2 shows the functional properties of the flour mixes. The outcome uncovered that there was tremendous contrast ($p < 0.05$) in the mass thickness, gelatinization limit, expanding power, water assimilation limit. The mass thickness of the samples went from 0.77 g/ml to 0.91 g/ml. Test A had the most elevated mass thickness of 0.91g/ml while test B had the least mass thickness of 0.77 g/ml. Test A was fundamentally unique ($p < 0.05$) from different samples dissected. This might be because of the particles size of the plantain flour with the exception of test B, the mass thickness results acquired from this study are higher than the discoveries of Ekperereka et al. (2020) who detailed lower upsides of mass thickness (0.77 g/ml) for ranch flours. Higher mass thickness is alluring for more prominent simplicity of dispersibility and decrease of glue thickness as it offers more critical pressing benefit (Amandikwa, 2012) while low thickness of flour is a decent actual trait while deciding transportation and storability.

The gelatinization limit of the samples went from 8.00 to 12.00. Test A was found to have the most elevated gelatinization limit and was fundamentally unique ($p < 0.05$) from different samples. The high gelatinization limit of test A proposes that it can frame gels more promptly than cocoyam flour (test B) and the other composite flour samples. Gelatinization limit is estimated by the capacity of an example to frame gel when warmed. Expanding power shows the level of openness of the interior design of the starch granules to the activity of water that is a proportion of hydration limit (Raules et al., 2006). The enlarging force of the samples was found to range from 29.12 to 34.02. Test A had the most elevated expanding power (34.02) and was fundamentally unique ($p < 0.05$) from the other samples. This is higher than the qualities revealed by Abioye et al. (2011) and Ielaboye (2019) for 100 percent plantain flour. This recommends that the plantain flour has higher capacity to grow when presented to water contrasted with the other flour samples. There was likewise a dynamic diminishing in expanding power as joining with cocoyam flour expanded. The decline noticed could be because of the impact of the cocoyam flour over the plantain flour as the starch cell walls of the cocoyam flour is not effectively separated by water. Water retention limit (WAC) of the flour samples went from 1.29 g/ml to 3.64 g/ml with test D having the most noteworthy. There was massive distinction ($P < 0.05$) in the WAC of the flour samples. WAC chiefly relies on protein and starches connections (Abiodun et al., 2012)

Table 2: Result for the Functional Properties of the Flour Samples.

Sample	BD(g/ml)	GC	SP(%)	WAC (ml/g)
A	0.91 ^a ±0.01	12.00 ^a ±0.003	4.02 ^a ±0.02	1.29 ^e ±0.01
B	0.77 ^c ±0.02	12.00 ^a ± 0.00	30.21 ^d ±0.01	2.45 ^b ±0.02
C	0.87 ^b ±0.01	10.00 ^b ± 0.00	32.53 ^b ±0.02	1.75 ^d ±0.01
D	0.78 ^c ±0.01	10.00 ^b ± 0.00	29.12 ^e ±0.01	3.64 ^a ±0.01
E	0.83 ^b ±0.02	8.00 ^c ± 0.00	31.72 ^c ±0.03	2.01 ^c ±0.01

Values are ± standard deviation of the duplicate determination. Means with different superscript within the same column are significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$).

Key:

A= Sample containing 100% plantain flour and 0% cocoyam flour

B= Sample containing 0% plantain flour and 100% cocoyam flour

C= Sample containing 60% plantain flour and 40% cocoyam flour

D= Sample containing 50% plantain flour and 50% cocoyam flour

E= Sample containing 40% plantain flour and 60% cocoyam flour,

BD= Bulk density, GC= Gelation capacity, SP= Swelling power, WAC= Water holding capacity

3.2. Result for pH Value of the Flour Samples

The pH is the level of corrosiveness or alkalinity of a substance. The pH result is introduced in table 3. The pH upsides of the flour mixes went from 5.88 to 6.75. Test B (cocoyam flour 100 percent) was found to have the most noteworthy pH (6.75) which was fundamentally unique in relation to different samples. This is upheld by discoveries by Adewale *et al.* (2016) who got comparable qualities for cocoyam flour. However, low pH values were seen in every one of the samples no matter their disparities.

Table 3: Result for pH Value of the Flour Samples

Samples	pH Value
A	6.36 ^d ±0.01
B	6.75 ^a ±0.01
C	6.51 ^c ±0.02
D	5.88 ^e ±0.01
E	6.61 ^b ±0.01

Values are ± standard deviation of the duplicate determination. Means with different superscript within the same column are significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$).

Key:

A= Sample containing 100% plantain flour and 0% cocoyam flour

B= Sample containing 0% plantain flour and 100% cocoyam flour

C= Sample containing 60% plantain flour and 40% cocoyam flour

D= Sample containing 50% plantain flour and 50% cocoyam flour

E= Sample containing 40% plantain flour and 60% cocoyam flour

3.3. Evaluation of the Antioxidant Properties of the Flour Samples

The result presented in Table 4 shows the antioxidant properties of the flour samples. There were massive contrast ($p < 0.05$) in the flavonoid, carotenoid and phenol items in the flour samples. The flavonoid content went from 0.67mg to 49.75mg. Test A was found to have the most reduced flavonoid content. Test B (100% cocoyam flour) recorded the most elevated flavonoid content. Flavonoids are essential in the rummaging of oxygen - got from free radicals. This proposes that the cocoyam flour and its plantain composites can give colossal health advantages.

The carotenoid content was found to go from 0.73 to 48.82. Test A (100 percent plantain flour) had the most elevated carotenoid content. This could be ascribed to the yellow shade of the plantain flour. Nonetheless, the carotenoid content diminished with fuse of cocoyam flour. This could be because of the impact of the low carotenoid content of the cocoyam flour (0.73) on the plantain flour.

The phenolic content went from 0.86 to 138.09. Test B recorded the most noteworthy phenolic content (138.09mgGAE) and was essentially unique ($p < 0.05$) from the other samples. Test A was found to contain the most reduced phenolic content (0.86), however, there was general

increment with joining of cocoyam flour. This implies that cocoyam flour is a decent wellspring of phenol. Lately, phenolics have attracted the interest of specialists since they show commitment of being strong cancer prevention agents that can safeguard the human body from free extremists, the arrangement of which is related with the typical digestion of vigorous cells (Oboh & Rocha, 2007).

Table 4: Results for the Antioxidant Properties of the Flour Samples

Sample	Total Flavonoid (Mg)	Carotenoid (μg)	Total Phenolic (MgGAE)
A	0.67 ^e ±0.02	48.82 ^a ±0.01	0.86 ^e ±0.02
B	49.75 ^a ±0.03	0.73 ^e ±0.01	138.09 ^a ±0.02
C	20.33 ^d ±0.01	30.16 ^b ±0.02	55.74 ^d ±0.03
D	25.23 ^c ±0.02	24.80 ^b ±0.01	69.48 ^c ±0.02
E	30.10 ^b ±0.02	19.95 ^d ±0.03	83.22 ^b ±0.01

Values are $\pm$ standard deviation of the duplicate determination. Means with different superscript within the same column are significantly different ($p \leq 0.05$)

Key:

A= Sample containing 100% plantain flour and 0% cocoyam flour

B= Sample containing 0% plantain flour and 100% cocoyam flour

C= Sample containing 60% plantain flour and 40% cocoyam flour

D= Sample containing 50% plantain flour and 50% cocoyam flour

E= Sample containing 40% plantain flour and 60% cocoyam flour

3.4. Evaluation of the Sensory Attributes of the Flour Samples

Sensory attributes of the flour samples are shown in table 5. Huge contrasts ($p < 0.05$) were seen in the appearance, mouldability, smell, mouth feel and in general acceptability. The appearance score went from 6.80 to 7.60. Test A recorded the most elevated score appearance (7.6) and was fundamentally unique ($p < 0.05$) from the rest. The presence of food varieties not set in stone by its tone. The higher appearance score of test A could be credited to its light yellow tone. Anyway there was no tremendous contrast ($p > 0.05$) in the appearance scores of tests C, D, and E. It may be attributed to the pale earthy colored shade of the cocoyam flour which has impacted the shade of the plantain flour. The mouldability score went from 5.74 to 7.7. Test A had the most elevated mouldability (7.7) and was fundamentally unique ($p < 0.05$) from different samples. This could be presumably because of the great mass thickness of test A which empowers it structure a bump without any problem. This proposes that test A is reasonable for creating a dumpling of high mouldability. There was no massive contrast ($p > 0.05$) in the mouldability scores of samples B to D.

The smell score to go from 6.4 to 7.10. Test A was found to have the most noteworthy fragrance score (7.10). This could be credited to the presence of fragrant mixtures or esters present in the plantain flour. Anyway there was no massive contrast ($p > 0.05$) in the fragrance score of the relative multitude of samples. The mouth-feel score went from 6.15 to 6.95. Test A was found to have the most elevated taste score (6.95). This could be credited to the sweet idea of plantain. Anyway there was no tremendous contrast ($p > 0.05$) in the taste score of the multitude of samples.

The general acceptability score went from 6.6 to 7.75. Test A had the most elevated acceptability score which shows that it was by and large OK contrasted with different samples. Anyway there was no massive contrast ($P>0.05$) in the general acceptability score of samples C, D and E.

Table 5: Result for the Sensory Properties of the Flour Samples

Samples	Appearance	Mouldability	Aroma	Mouth Feel	Overall Accept.
A	7.60 ^a ±0.94	7.70 ^a ±1.13	7.10 ^a ±1.33	6.95 ^a ±1.67	7.75 ^a ±1.21
B	7.00 ^{ab} ±1.34	6.05 ^b ±1.76	6.40 ^a ±1.23	6.55 ^a ±1.39	7.10 ^{ab} ±1.25
C	6.80 ^b ±0.89	6.15 ^b ±1.69	6.50 ^a ±0.83	6.15 ^a ±1.04	6.60 ^b ±0.75
D	7.11 ^{ab} ±1.05	5.74 ^b ±1.66	6.74 ^a ±1.24	6.68 ^a ±0.89	6.84 ^b ±0.83
E	7.15 ^{ab} ±0.99	6.10 ^b ±1.48	6.75 ^a ±1.02	6.75 ^a ±1.29	6.90 ^b ±1.33

Values are ± standard deviation of the duplicate determination. Means with different superscript within the same column are significantly different ($p\leq 0.05$).

Key:

- A= Sample containing 100% plantain flour and 0% cocoyam flour
- B= Sample containing 0% plantain flour and 100% cocoyam flour
- C= Sample containing 60% plantain flour and 40% cocoyam flour
- D= Sample containing 50% plantain flour and 50% cocoyam flour
- E= Sample containing 40% plantain flour and 60 % cocoyam flour

4. Conclusion

This study has uncovered that amala can be created from unripe plantain and cocoyam flour mixes. In any case, plantain flour is best reasonable for making amala contrasted with cocoyam flour because of its high mass thickness, enlarging power and gelatinization limit. Plantain and cocoyam flour will generally be moderately restricting in certain phytochemicals however blend of the two flours expanded their phytochemical contents. Amala produced using 100 percent plantain flour was preferred most as regards sensory characteristics. Further research needs to be carried out to find ways of reducing the oxalate content of cocoyam flour.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declared no conflict of interest.

Author Contributions

NLN, AUN, JNO, COA, IIO and CU proposed the study, designed it, generated the data and wrote the manuscript. The authors also approved the final draft of the manuscript.

Data Availability Statement

The original contributions presented in the study are included in the article. Further enquiries can be directed to the corresponding author.

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